

Étienne Nodet. *A Gate to Heaven: Essenes, Qumran: Origins and Heirs*. Jewish and Christian Texts in Context and Related Studies 37. London: T&T Clark, 2023. Hardback. 252 pages \$159.95. ISBN 978567709714.

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A Gate to Heaven: Essenes, Qumran: Origins and Heirs is an English translation of Étienne Nodet's volume *La Porte du Ciel. Révélation sur Qumrân et les Esséniens* (Cerf, 2016). Nodet's central thesis is set forth at the beginning of the volume, namely, that from the 1st century BCE onward the site of Khirbet Qumran functioned as a place of pilgrimage for the Essenes, whom he suggests is a collection of rural Jewish communities spread throughout Syria-Palestine. According to Nodet, Essenes came to Qumran to commemorate a renewal of the Israelite entry into the Promised Land under the direction of Joshua. Nodet further suggests that the well-organized cemetery at Qumran was a locus for Essene burials, as the site of Khirbet Qumran was seen "symbolically as the portal to heaven" (1). Nodet also argues in the volume that the Essene movement did not disappear after the war in 70 CE, as is often held, but rather that its institutions and customs had an influence on nascent Christianity and rabbinic Judaism.

Nodet begins the book with a brief overview of his argument, including an outline of the chapters and the primary sources that he consulted. He writes that these sources will be examined from a historical perspective, particularly concerning the development of institutions and associated conflicts, as well as from a sociological perspective, specifically the structure of movements and their construction of identity. Chapter 1 focuses on the discovery of the Dead Sea Scrolls and subsequent discussions regarding the identity of the movement that lies behind the Scrolls, which Nodet accepts as being the Essenes. Nodet also accepts Jean-Baptiste Humbert's revised archaeological interpretation of the development of the site (2006, 2016), which suggests the presence of a villa abandoned somewhere between 63–57 BCE and a subsequent community center inhabited by a small group of Essenes. This revised interpretation of the site, according to Nodet, lowers the chronology of the Essenes and reduces the capacity for permanent habitation of the site, creating a tension between a small permanent group and the larger development of the site, including the advanced water system and the large well-organized cemetery at the site. Nodet's central thesis attempts to explain this tension.

Chapters 2 and 3 present a detailed reconstruction of the political history of Judea and Judaism from the 5th century through the 2nd century BCE as well as an overview of the Jewish parties in this period. As he reconstructs this period, Nodet's knowledge and use of primary source is extensive. He argues that the political and ideological considerations of this period are far more complex than has been previously understood. Discussing the Jewish parties of the day, Nodet offers a focused development of the Essene movement (107–115), which provides the basis for the following chapters. For Nodet, there are strong analogies between the Sadducees and the Essenes, specifically regarding calendrical traditions and a shared concern for biblical interpretation. Nodet reconstructs the Essene movement through the lens of classical sources, but also through what he ascribes as being "the main internal documents describing the Essenes," the Damascus Document and the Community Rule, and admitting that the overall picture is somewhat complex (107).

Chapters 4 and 5 focus on the impact of the Essene movement on early Christianity and rabbinic literature, respectively. Here, Nodet spends the bulk of his time discussing baptism as a common practice between the Essenes and early Christians, as well as the incorporation of Essene customs in later rabbinic Judaism. It is this latter discussion that poses the most challenge to scholarly consensus. Nodet concludes the volume with some final remarks in which he offers an overview of the historical and ideological dimensions of the Essene movement. According to Nodet's reconstruction, the Essene movement, while often considered more peripheral, are much more centered in the religious milieu of the Second Temple period, with their shadow extending even into later rabbinic literature.

Returning to Nodet's central thesis, there are only a few sustained discussions regarding the role of Khirbet Qumran within the Essene movement (see 118–121 in particular). This leaves the impression that the volume is more a historical and ideological reconstruction of Essene movement within the larger Jewish landscape than an exploration of the role of Khirbet Qumran within the movement. To his point, the argument that Khirbet Qumran was a place of pilgrimage for the Essene movement, while intriguing and worthy of greater development, remains largely unconvincing. Particularly important to Nodet's thesis is Pliny's description of the Essenes in *Natural History* (5.15.73; cf. 18), a description Nodet reads as reflecting a regular pilgrimage to Qumran. The description, on the other hand, appears to describe newcomers joining the "solitary tribe" of the Essenes: "Day by day, the throng of refugees is recruited to an equal number by numerous accessions of persons tired of life and driven thither by the waves of fortune to adopt their manners," thus maintaining the celibate community "through thousands of ages" (Rackham, LCL).

Whether or not one is convinced by Nodet's conclusions, the volume is creative and boundary-pushing. As the preface to the book notes, Nodet sought to take the road less traveled and not follow the crowd. While some of his scholarship is "intermittently controversial" (xi), Nodet's work remains unique and probing. This volume continues the tradition of his life's work.

Michael DeVries is an adjunct professor at Azusa Pacific University.